

On the Change of Mechanical Properties of Glass Fiber Reinforced Cements by Two Years Outdoor Exposure

K. Sakaguchi¹⁾, K. Kikui¹⁾, T. Fujii²⁾, Z. Maekawa²⁾, K. Otani²⁾

- 1) Kurimoto Iron Works, Ltd., 12-19, Kitahorie 1-chome, Nishi-ku, Osaka 550, Japan
2) Osaka City University, 3-138, Sugimoto 3-chome, Sumiyoshi-ku, Osaka 558, Japan

ABSTRACT

Using the combined continuous and discontinuous alkali-resistant glass fiber reinforced cements, the change of the mechanical properties are measured under the condition of outdoor exposure. In order to explain the change of these mechanical properties, the various considerations on the hardening phenomena of cements, the increase of critical fiber length and the increase of the micro mechanical friction at the interface between fiber and cement matrix, etc. are described.

INTRODUCTION

Many kinds of the reinforcing materials are used in cements and concretes in order to improve the low tensile and flexural strengths and the easy occurrence of crack. Since steel reinforced cement is not always enough to resist the crack occurrence, the alkali-resistant glass fiber has been developed as one of the reinforcements which can improve the resistance of crack occurrence. Though the applications of glass fiber reinforced cements (GRC) have been expanding up to the present, it is used only for the secondary structural materials. The reason may be considered that the reinforcing effect is not always enough one for the sake of the discontinuity of the chopped strand fibers which are generally used as the reinforcements of GRC. Thus, we consider that the more useful reinforcing effect may be obtained by the combination of the chopped strand fibers and the continuous fibers.

In this paper, we examine the change of the mechanical properties of two years outdoor exposure of GRC reinforced by the discontinuous and continuous glass fibers, and discuss about the influence of the continuous fibers on the mechanical properties of GRC.

TESTING METHOD AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The constitutions of GRC used in this experiment are shown in Table 1. The representative production techniques of GRC are two kinds of the injection molding method and the direct spray method, and the latter method is adopted in present work. The GRC sheets are finished with roller to 6-9 mm thickness, cured for 7 days in wet condition and then laid for 2 months in air. This sample is called by "A", and the sample added 5% polymer additive to "A" is called by "S".

After curing, these sheets are cut into the size of 800 x 350 mm. These are faced due south and are inclined at 45° angle to the level surface on the roof of the building as shown in Figure 1. The meteorological data of Osaka prefecture for the exposure period are shown in Figure 2. All data except the solar energy are quoted from "THE Monthly Report of the Japan Meteorological Agency". The solar energy are measured by the pyrheliometer which are mounted on the exposure stage together with the samples.

Four kinds of the tests are carried out in order to examine the tensile strength, the flexural strength, the elastic modulus and the frequency loss coefficient of GRC during the exposure period. The configurations of the test specimens are illustrated in Figure 3.

Tensile Strength and Elastic Modulus

Static tensile tests are carried out in room temperature by using the Instron type test machine (Shimadzu auto-graph DSS-5000 type) under the cross-head speed of 2 mm/min.

First, the mechanical characteristics of GRC sheets before exposure are examined. The reinforcing properties of GRC sheets are considered to be changed by the combination of the continuous and discontinuous fibers. Figure 4 shows the relation between the tensile strength and the elastic modulus of GRC before exposure and the loading angle, where the loading angle means the angle between loading direction and the principal axis of continuous fiber cloth. As shown in this figure, the influence of the loading angle on the tensile strength and the elastic modulus appears slightly. This effect is considered to be caused by the anisotropic properties of the continuous fibers.

Next, the relation between the tensile modulus and the outdoor exposure time is shown in Figure 5. Comparing the results of before exposure with after exposure, the tensile elastic moduli of the specimens A and S are gradually increased, and the elastic modulus of A is greater than that of S. It is proved from these results that the elastic modulus of GRC depends on mainly the matrix phase which becomes hard as the exposure time increases.

Figure 6 shows the relation between the tensile strengths of GRC and the outdoor exposure time. The tensile strengths of A and S have a tendency to decrease as the exposure time increases, contrary to the elastic modulus. In the early exposure time, the tensile strength of A is greater than that of S and the difference of both tensile strengths decreases as the exposure time increases.

Figure 7 shows the stress-strain curves of A and S materials. These curves give the straight lines up to the stress level of 0.3-0.5 kgf/mm² and the strain level of 0.015-0.025%. With the increase of load, the stress-strain curves bend into second stage. In this stage, the pull out and the fracture of fibers occur continuously until the final fracture of specimen. This phenomena are considered as the ductile behavior different from that of cement mortar.

Flexural Strength

The 3 point bending tests are carried out for the specimen shown in Figure 3(b). The span length is 150mm and the cross head speed is 5 mm/min. Figure 8 shows the relation between the flexural strength of GRC and the outdoor exposure time. The flexural strengths of A and S decrease as the exposure time increases, and the decrease of A is greater than that of S. It is observed from this results that the effect of the polymer additive on the flexural strength of GRC increases as the exposure time increases.

Frequency Loss Coefficient

The frequency loss coefficients of GRC are measured in the room temperature for the cantilever specimen shown in Figure 3(d) by use of the complex modulus apparatus. The span length is 200mm. The frequency loss coefficients are obtained from the first, second and third resonant frequencies in the forced vibration test. Figure 9 shows the relation between the frequency loss coefficient and the exposure time. As shown in this figure, it is observed that the frequency loss coefficient of S decreases slightly greater than that of A as the exposure time increases.

DISCUSSION ON THE CHANGE OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES BY OUTDOOR EXPOSURE

The changes of mechanical properties of GRC under the outdoor exposure are affected by the temperature and the humidity of atmosphere, and the amounts of rainfall and solar energy etc.. The tensile elastic modulus of GRC is calculated by use of next equation,

$$E_c = fV_f E_f + (1-V_f)E_m, \quad f = \frac{\sum a_n \cos^4 \phi}{n} \quad (1)$$

,where

- E_f : elastic modulus of fiber
- E_m : elastic modulus of matrix (cements)
- V_f : volume fraction of fiber
- f : coefficient of the orientation pattern of fiber
- ϕ : angle of fiber orientation

Majumdar(1) carried out the tensile test on the fibers after GRC had been exposed in air or in water for the period up to 1,200 days, and found that the strength reduction of fibers in air was very small. Choen and Diamond(2) observed no change in the strength of fibers after 500 days of exposure. It can be considered from these results that the change of the elastic modulus of fibers during exposure is very small. According to the BRE report(3), the ratio of the elastic modulus after sufficiently long exposure time to that of before exposure is 1.25-1.28 after 5 year exposure. Hence, the change of E_f , V_f and f are smaller than that of E_m during exposure, and then we consider the next equation.

$$(E_m)_t = E_{mt} = \xi E_{m0} (1 - ae^{-t}) \quad (2)$$

,where

$$\xi = (E_m)_{t \rightarrow \infty} / (E_m)_{t=0} = E_{m\infty} / E_{m0} \quad (3)$$

hence

$$a = 1 - (1/\xi) \quad (4)$$

Then, we obtain

$$\frac{E_{ct}}{E_{co}} = 1 + \frac{(-1 + \xi - \xi ae^{-t})}{\left(\frac{fV_f E_f}{(1-V_f)E_{m0}} + 1 \right)} \quad (5)$$

The solid lines in Figure 5 are the results of calculation of Eq.(5).

The stress and strain relation of GRC is characterized by two stages. The first stage is the linear elastic range up to the bending point in the stress and strain relation, and the second stage appears according to the increase of stress. The behavior in the second stage is in-elastic, but the stress and strain relation is nearly linearly as shown in Figure 7. The applied stress of GRC in the first stage is

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_c = & (\text{stress in the continuous fiber phase})(\text{volume fraction of the} \\ & \text{continuous fiber phase}) + (\text{stress in the discontinuous fiber phase}) \\ & (\text{volume fraction of the discontinuous fiber phase}) + (\text{stress in the} \\ & \text{matrix phase})(\text{volume fraction of the matrix phase}) \\ = & f_{cont} V_{fcont} \sigma_{fcont} + f_{disc} \left(1 - \frac{\lambda}{2L} \right) V_{fdisc} \sigma_{fdisc} + (1 - V_{fcont} - V_{fdisc}) \sigma_{mu} \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

,where

$$\lambda_c = (\sigma_{fu} / 2\tau_m) d_f \quad (7)$$

,where λ_c is the critical fiber length and d_f is the diameter of fiber.

The changes of the stresses at the limit of proportionality and fracture may depend on the decrease of interfacial shearing strength and the increase of critical fiber length. Though the change of the strength of matrix may be exist, it is considered that the amount is smaller than the change of the interfacial strength. The ratio of the stress at the exposure time of t to at before exposure becomes as

$$\frac{\sigma_{ct}}{\sigma_{co}} = 1 + \frac{\frac{l_{co}}{2l} (1 - \frac{l_{ct}}{l_{co}})}{\left(\frac{f_{cont} v_{fcont}}{f_{disc} v_{fdisc}} + (1 - \frac{l_{co}}{2l}) + \frac{(1 - v_{fdisc} - v_{fcont})}{v_{fdisc}} \cdot \frac{1}{f_{disc}} \frac{\sigma_{mo}}{\sigma_{fu}} \right)} + \frac{\left(\frac{\sigma_{mt}}{\sigma_{mo}} - 1 \right)}{\frac{f_{cont}}{(1 - v_{fdisc} - v_{fcont})} \frac{\sigma_{fu}}{\sigma_{mo}} + \frac{f_{disc} (1 - \frac{l_{co}}{2l}) v_{fdisc} \sigma_{fu}}{(1 - v_{fdisc} - v_{fcont}) \sigma_{mo}} + 1} \quad (8)$$

According to the BRE data(3), we estimate the amounts of l_{ct}/l_{co} by the 5 years exposure. Table 2 shows the change of l_{ct}/l_{co} by the exposure time. Under the assumption that the contribution of the matrix at fracture is small, the tensile strength of the combined continuous and dis continuous alkali-resistant glass fiber reinforced cement is given by

$$\sigma_{cu} = f_{cont} v_{fcont} \sigma_{fu} + f_{disc} \left(1 - \frac{l_{ct}}{2l} \right) v_{fdisc} \sigma_{fu} \quad (9)$$

The numerical results are illustrated as the solid lines in Figure 6.

There are the damping property, dynamic modulus and frequency response, etc. as the special characteristics of vibration of GRC specimen. As mentioned in previous description, we measured the damping properties by using the cantilever specimen. The change of the damping properties of GRC is considered to be mainly depended on the interface characteristic between fibers and cements. In order to explain the damping properties of GRC, we propose a mechanical model as shown in Figure 10. This model is composed of two sets of the linear springs with the different spring constants and one solid friction element. The property of the solid friction corresponds to the interface characteristics affected by outdoor exposure. The stress and strain relation is given by

$$\sigma = \frac{2E_1 E_2}{(E_1 + E_2)} \epsilon \pm \frac{(E_2 - E_1)}{(E_1 + E_2)} F_{max} \quad (+: \text{tension}, -: \text{compression}) \quad (10)$$

, where F_{max} is the sliding force in the solid friction element. When F is less than F_{max} , σ is described as

$$\sigma = \frac{(E_1 + E_2)}{2} \epsilon - (E_2 - E_1) \epsilon_0 \quad (11)$$

Then, in the range of $\epsilon > \epsilon_m$ the work of one cycle of vibration is

$$w = k C_1 C_2 (\epsilon_m \epsilon - \epsilon_m^2) \quad (12)$$

, where $k = \frac{2(E_2 - E_1)^2}{(E_1 + E_2)}$ (13)

C_1 ; the coefficient of the state of interface
 C_2 ; the coefficient of the mode of vibration

ϵ_m means the strain when the micro interfacial slipping occurs and is shown as follows;

$$\epsilon_m = \frac{2}{(E_2 - E_1)} F_{max} \quad (14)$$

The coefficients of equivalent damping property is

$$D_{eq} = \frac{C_1 C_2 (\epsilon_m \epsilon - \epsilon_m^2)}{2\pi \epsilon^2} \quad (15)$$

The effect of the outdoor exposure is considered to appear remarkably on the change of the coefficient C_1 . This coefficient may be divided into two parts. One is the coefficient about discontinuous fiber and the other is that about continuous fiber, that is ,

$$C_1 = C_{1cont} + C_{1disc} \quad (16)$$

On the other hand, the change of the damping property of specimen A is very small in comparison with specimen S. Then, C_1 is assumed to be as follows;

$$\begin{aligned} (C_1)_{\text{specimen A}} &= C_{1A} = (C_{1A})_{t=0} = C_{1Ao} \\ (C_1)_{\text{specimen S}} &= C_{1S} = C_{1Ao} (1 - be^{-t}) \end{aligned}$$

The ratio of the equivalent damping at exposure time of t to at before exposure is given as

$$\frac{(D_{eq})_t}{(D_{eq})_0} = \frac{C_{1At}/C_{1Ao}}{(1+C_{1So}/C_{1Ao})} + \frac{(1-be^{-t})}{(1+C_{1So}/C_{1Ao})} \quad (17)$$

The solid lines in Figure 9 are written from the numerical results.

CONCLUSION

The change of the mechanical properties of alkali-resistant glass fiber reinforced cements under the condition of outdoor exposure in two years has been observed. Because of good load sharing property, we add two plies of roving cloth to the usual GRC which is reinforced by chopped fibers. The results of tests show good mechanical properties and the effect of the additive material in cements.

The exposure effect is apparently associated with the hardening phenomena of cement mortar, the increase of the critical fiber length and the increase of the micro mechanical friction at the interface between fiber and cement matrix.

There is an obvious need to extend the investigation to longer times and the behaviour of interface under such conditions is, in fact, to be the subject of further studies.

REFERENCES

- (1) Majumdar, A.J., 'Properties of fiber cement composites', Fiber Reinforced Cement and Concrete, RILEM Symposium, 1975, pp.279-313.
- (2) Cohen, E.B., and Diamond, S., 'Validity of flexural strength reduction as an indication of alkali attack on glass in fiber reinforced cement composites', Fiber Reinforced Cement and Concrete, RILEM Symposium, 1975, pp.315-325.
- (3) BRE reports, 'A study of the properties of Cem-FIL/OPC Composites', Building Research Establishment Current Paper, CP 38/76, June 1976.

Figure 1. The exposure stage on the roof of the building.
 Building: C-building in campus of faculty of Engineering, Osaka City University
 Height : 15 m

Figure 2. The change of the weathering condition at the exposure period.

Figure 4. Angle between continuous fiber direction and loading direction

Figure 3. Configuration of specimen

- (a) Tensile strength test
- (b) Flexural strength test
- (c) Tensile elastic modulus test
- (d) Vibration test

Table 1. The constitution of experimental materials

Matrix phase	
Normal portland cement	
Sand cement ratio	:0.7
Water cement ratio	0.32
Dispersed phase	
Chopped strand glass fiber	
Diameter of filament	: 13 μ m
Length	: 35mm
Weight content	: 4 %
Continuous glass fiber	
Roving cloth	410 g/mm ²
Number of ply	: 0,2

Figure 5. The relation between tensile elastic modulus and exposure period

Figure 6. The relation between tensile strength and exposure period

Figure 7. The stress - strain curves of GRC

Figure 8. The relation between flexural strength and exposure period

Figure 10. Mechanical model of vibration.

Figure 9. The relation between frequency loss coefficient and exposure period

Table 2. The relation between l_{ct}/l_{co} and the exposure period.

Exposure time	l_{ct}/l_{co}
initial	1.0
1 year	2.28
5 year	4.0